

Spring long-legged flies (Diptera, Dolichopodidae) from Vitosha Mountain, with first record for the Balkan Peninsula: second contribution

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Abstract: The present paper gives information about spring dolichopodids collected from April to June in Vitosha Mountain, Bulgaria. Twenty-five species were found, as thirteen are new for the studied area and one of them (*Achalcus cinereus* (Haliday in Walker, 1851)) is new to the fauna of Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula too.

Keywords: *Achalcus cinereus*, Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria, Dolichopodidae, new records, Vitosha Mountain

Introduction

The family Dolichopodidae belongs to the superfamily Empidoidea of the suborder Brachycera, order Diptera. The family is widespread in all zoogeographic areas of the planet, without Antarctic. Today approximately 8300 species from 261 genera are described worldwide (Grichanov, 2023). For the fauna of Bulgaria are known 214 species. Most species of the family Dolichopodidae are found in humid habitats: on vegetation around rivers, lakes, streams, marshes, flooded forests, etc. As predators, the species of the family play an important role in the regulation of a number of pests in forests and other natural ecosystems.

The first contribution of the Dolichopodidae family (Kechev et al., 2024) for Vitosha Mountain summarised the information about forty-one species (old and new records) from the area. The main purpose of the new contribution is to give new information about the distribution of the family Dolichopodidae in Vi-

tosha Mountain, new data for Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula and new records of the species in the investigated region.

Material and methods

The material for the present work was collected by means of sweep net from 23 localities in Vitosha Mountain. The main characteristics of the localities are shown below and on Fig. 1. The material was collected during the spring in the period from the beginning of April to the mid of June 2024. After collection, the adults were put in vials containing 95% ethanol. The species were sorted in the laboratory, using a stereo microscope, Carl Zeiss. For the determination of dolichopodids were used identification guides mainly by Parent (1938), d'Assis Fonseca (1978), Grichanov (2007) and Negrobov & Stackelberg (1969). The faunistic list includes the following information: name of the species, material (male and

Fig. 1. Map of Vitosha Mountain with localities.

female) and sites of collection. Species new to the fauna of the Vitosha Mountain are marked with one asterisk (*) and about the species new to Bulgaria and the Balkan Peninsula are used two asterisks (**). The material presented in this paper as new to the Vitosha Mt is housed in Mihail Kechev's collection in the Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Department of Forest Entomology, Phytopathology and Game Fauna, Sofia, Bulgaria.

Main characteristics of the localities:

Site 1: above residential area Knyazevo, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6549°N 23.2425°E, 749 m.

Site 2: Rudartsi Lake, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5851°N 23.1631°E, 779 m.

Site 3: Studena Dam (Fig. 2C), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5459°N 23.1610°E, 854 m.

Fig. 2. Habitats: A – Struma River above Chuipetlovo Village; B – Palakariya River near Yarlovo Village; C – Studena Dam; D – Konyarnika Area.

Site 4: Bosnek Village (Struma River), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5017°N 23.1595°E, 899 m.

Site 5: Simeonovo lakes, meadow, 42.6074°N 23.3299°E, 948 m.

Site 6: Byalata Voda Area, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6415°N 23.2305°E, 976 m.

Site 7: above Dragalevtsi Monastery (Dragalevska River), forest vegetation, 42.6201°N 23.3009°E, 1008 m.

Fig. 3. *Achalcus cinereus* (Haliday in Walker, 1851): habitus.

Site 8: Boyana Lake, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6361°N 23.2698°E, 1054 m.

Site 9: Tihya Kut Area, meadow, 42.6393°N 23.2202°E, 1058 m.

Site 10: above Bistritsa Village (Bistrishka River), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5863°N 23.3381°E, 1082 m.

Site 11: above Yarlovo Village (Palakaria River) (Fig. 2B), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.4759°N 23.2767°E, 1120 m.

Site 12: above Kladnitsa Village (Tanchovitsa River), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5670°N 23.1956°E, 1131 m.

Site 13: Dendrarium Area, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6282°N 23.2298°E, 1201 m.

Site 14: Yarema Area (Kurtova River), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5077°N 23.3334°E, 1232 m.

Site 15: Chuyetlovo Village (Struma River) (Fig. 2A), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5224°N 23.2457°E, 1273 m.

Site 16: Pazarishteto Area (Vladayska River), hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6130°N 23.2268°E, 1325 m.

Site 17: Zlatni Mostove Area, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6102°N 23.2362°E, 1392 m.

Site 18: above Kikish Shelter, forest vegetation, 42.6170°N 23.2871°E, 1407 m.

Site 19: Septemvri Hut, hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.6186°N 23.2434°E, 1477 m.

Site 20: Tintyava Hut, forest vegetation, 42.6217°N 23.2534°E, 1526 m.

Site 21: Vetrovala Area, meadow, 42.5956°N 23.2363°E, 1578 m.

Site 22: Kumata Hut, forest vegetation, 42.5951°N 23.2494°E, 1694 m.

Site 23: Konyarnika Area (Fig. 2D), highland hydrophyte grasses and shrubs, 42.5917°N 23.2462°E, 1765 m.

Faunistic results

Achalcinae

** *Achalcus cinereus* (Haliday in Walker, 1851) (Fig. 3). Material examined: Site 15: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♂, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

Diaphorinae

* *Chrysotus femoratus* Zetterstedt, 1843. Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

* *Chrysotus pulchellus* Kowarz, 1875. Material examined: Site 13: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Dolichopodinae

* *Dolichopus griseipennis* Stannius, 1831. Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 4 ♀♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

* *Dolichopus nubilus* Meigen, 1824. Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 7 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 3: 27.v.2024, 3 ♂♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

* *Dolichopus picipes* Meigen, 1824. Material examined: Site 23: 2.vi.2024, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Dolichopus signifer Haliday, 1838. Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 16 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

* *Hercostomus nanus* (Macquart, 1827). Material examined: Site 1: 9.vi.2024, 1 ♂; 16.vi.2024, 1 ♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

* *Hercostomus vivax* (Loew, 1857). Material examined: Site 1: 9.vi.2024, 4 ♂♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Sybistroma discipes (Germar, 1817). Material examined: Site 1: 9.vi.2024, 1 ♂; Site 6: 15.vi.2024, 1 ♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Fig. 4. *Rhaphium crassipes* (Meigen, 1824): habitus.

Hydrophorinae

Hydrophorus balticus (Meigen, 1824). Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 2 ♀♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 22: 2.vi.2024, 1 ♀; Site 21: same date, 1 ♂; Site 23: same date, 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Hydrophorus bipunctatus (Lehmann, 1822). Material examined: Site 23: 2.vi.2024, 2 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Medeterinae

Medetera jacula (Fallén, 1823). Material examined: Site 1: 16.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Thrypticus divisus (Strobl, 1880). Material examined: Site 3: 27.v.2024, 1 ♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

Rhaphiinae

Rhaphium appendiculatum Zetterstedt, 1849. Material examined: Site 1: 1.iv.2024, 1 ♀; 9.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂; Site 6: 1.iv.2024, 1 ♀; Site 16: 4.iv.2024, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova; Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 12: 27.v.2024, 1 ♀; Site 5: 27.v.2024, 1 ♂, 7 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 3

♂♂, 1 ♀; Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

* *Rhaphium brevicorne* Curtis, 1835. Material examined: Site 13: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

* *Rhaphium crassipes* (Meigen, 1824). Material examined: Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

* *Rhaphium monotrichum* Loew, 1850. Material examined: Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 3 ♂♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Sciapodinae

* *Sciapus platypterus* (Fabricius, 1805). Material examined: Site 1: 9.vi.2024, 5 ♀♀; 16.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 1 ♀; 15.vi.2024, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Sympycninae

Campsicnemus curvipes (Fallén, 1823). Material examined: Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 8: 31.v.2024, 2 ♂♂; Site 23: 2.vi.2024, 1 ♂; Site 21: same date, 1 ♂; Site 19: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂; Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 6 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; Site 1: 9.vi.2024, 1 ♀; 16.vi.2024, 4 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀; Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; 15.vi.2024, 3 ♂♂, 5 ♀♀; Site 9: 16.vi.2024, 1 ♂, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Campsicnemus umbripennis Loew, 1856. Material examined: Site 1: 5.v.2024, 1 ♀, Site 18: same date, 1 ♂; Site 5: 27.v.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Site 8: 31.v.2024, 1 ♂; Site 23: 2.vi.2024, 1 ♀; Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 1 ♀; 15.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂, 8 ♀♀; Site 9: 16.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Sympycnus pulicarius (Fallén, 1823). Material examined: Site 10: 24.iv.2024, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 13: 5.v.2024, 2 ♂♂; Site 5: 27.v.2024, 8 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; Site 2: same date, 5 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 8: 31.v.2024, 9 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀; Site 7: same date, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀; Site 19: 8.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀; Site 17: same date, 5 ♂♂, 11 ♀♀; Site 13: same date, 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Site 20: same date, 3 ♂♂; Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 30 ♂♂, 39 ♀♀; 15.vi.2024, 9 ♂♂, 14 ♀♀; Site 1: 16.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

* *Syntormon metathesis* (Loew, 1850). Material examined: Site 3: 27.v.2024, 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

Syntormon pallipes (Fabricius, 1794). Material examined: Site 1: 4.iv.2024, 3 ♂♂; 8.iv.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 5.v.2024, 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀; 16.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova; Site 15: 16.iv.2024, 4 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀; Site 4: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♀, Site 3: 16.iv.2024, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 11: 24.iv.2024, 3 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 14: 24.iv.2024, 1 ♀, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev; Site 5: 27.v.2024, 8 ♂♂, 9 ♀♀; Site 8: 31.v.2024, 3 ♂♂; Site 22: 2.vi.2024, 1 ♀; Site 21: same date, 1 ♂; Site 20: 8.vi.2024, 5 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Site 6: 10.vi.2024, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 15.vi.2024, 1 ♂, 4 ♀♀, leg. G. Zaemdzhikova.

Syntormon pumilum (Meigen, 1824). Material examined: Site 11: 16.v.2024, 1 ♂, leg. M. Kechev, G. Zaemdzhikova, B. Koychev.

Discussion

Twenty-five species of the long-legged flies were collected in Vitosha Mountain during the spring months in 2024. Thirteen of them are new to the investigated area, as *A. cinereus* is new to the Balkan Peninsula.

Genus *Achalculus* was revised by Pollet (1996), where nine Palaearctic species were given. Negrobov & Selivanova (2010) described other one species – *A. polleti* Negrobov & Selivanova, 2010 from Amur Region, Russia. To the fauna of the Balkan Peninsula only two species of the genus are known – *A. flavicollis* (Meigen, 1824) was reported by Pollet (1996) Kranevo, Baltata Forest, Bulgaria and Pollet & Ivković (2018) found one female specimen of *A. phragmitidis* Pollet, 1996 from Roški Slap, Krka River, Croatia. *A. cinereus* (Fig. 3) reported in this work as new to the Balkans was found along the riversides in hydrophyte vegetation within deciduous and coniferous forests. The two Bulgarian *Achalculus* species are easily distinguished by the thorax colouration – in *A. flavicollis* the thorax is yellow, but in *A. cinereus* it is dark green.

Rhaphium crassipes (Fig. 4) is known for the Balkan Peninsula from Traù (Trogir), Croatia (Strobl, 1904). In the previous literature, this species is wrongly reported for the fauna of Bulgaria. However, this research confirms the presence of *Rh. crassipes* for Bulgaria. As in the second half of the summer (Kechev et al., 2024), during the spring *S. pulicarius* was collected with a large number of specimens from

10 localities in Vitosha Mountain. The species is known from a lot of sites in Bulgaria from different altitudes – from the sea level to 2000 m (Kechev et al., 2022). *S. pulicarius* is a widespread species over Europe and there are several synonyms mentioned during the years (*S. annulipes* (Meigen, 1824), *S. pygmaeus* (Macquart, 1827), *S. cinerellus* (Zetterstedt, 1838) and *S. desoutteri* Parent, 1925). Pollet et al. (2015) conducted extensive research on this topic and clarified the problems with the synonyms. Along with this, the authors describe a new species of *Sympycnus* – *S. septentrionalis* Pollet, Persson, Bøggild & Crossley, 2015 which dwelling the same habitats as *S. pulicarius*, but spread mainly in northern European countries (Britain, Denmark, Finland, Germany and Sweden). In further studies of the higher parts of the mountains in Bulgaria and other Balkan countries, where the climate and habitats are similar to those in the north, there is a possibility *S. septentrionalis* that it will also be found in the Balkans.

The third locality of *S. metathesis* for the Balkans is given in this study. The species is known from Ohrid Lake, North Macedonia (Coe, 1960) and Gradina Floodplain Forest, Bulgaria (Kechev, 2012).

With this research the total number of the dolichopodid species for Vitosha Mountain is increasing to 54 and to the fauna of Bulgaria 215 species.

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